

Semimicro and Macro Titrimetric Method for Determination of Hg(II) and the Associated Free Acid using *N*-Benzenesulphonylglycine

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The method for the determination of Hg(II) and the associated free acid has been developed on the macro and semimicro scale. The amount of alkali, required to titrate Hg(II) solution containing free acid in presence of an excess of $\text{PhSO}_2\text{NHCH}_2\text{CO}_2^-$ with phenolphthalein as indicator, represents the total amount of free acid and Hg(II). When excess KI is added to this titrated solution, alkali, equivalent to the amount of Hg(II), is liberated, which is titrated with a standard acid, providing the amount of Hg(II). By difference, the free acid is calculated. Among the ions sulphate, acetate, chloride, and Cu(II) in small amounts do not interfere.

The present communication describes a method by which Hg(II) and the associated free acid can be determined simultaneously on macro and semimicro scales, using *N*-benzenesulphonylglycine as the reagent.

The reagent, $\text{PhSO}_2\text{NHCH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ (*N*-benzenesulphonylglycine), is monobasic, but may be represented as RH_2 . It forms complexes¹ with bivalent metals, e.g., $\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{R}_2$ where, $\text{M}^{\text{II}} = \text{Cu(II)}, \text{Zn(II)}, \text{Hg(II)}$ and $\text{M}^{\text{I}} = \text{H}^+, \text{Na}^+, \text{K}^+$, etc. The dissociation constant of the hydrogen attached to nitrogen increases so much on complex formation that it becomes possible to titrate with an alkali in the cases of H_2CuR_2 and H_2HgR_2 , affording stable complex salts.

When an Hg(II) solution, containing free acid, is titrated with a standard alkali in presence of phenolphthalein and an excess of RH^- (RH_2 made neutral to phenolphthalein with KOH), firstly the free acid is neutralised and then there occurs the following reaction on adding further alkali:

The amount of alkali consumed is equivalent to the sum of the free acid and twice the amount of Hg(II) present. On adding excess of KI to this neutralised solution, HgR_2^{2-} reacts according to the following equation:

The moles of alkali liberated are twice those of Hg present and this deep pink solution is titrated with standard H_2SO_4 to decolorisation, providing the amount of Hg present. By difference with the first titration, the amount of free acid may be calculated.

In presence of Cu(II), the first titration is equivalent to the total amount of free acid, Cu(II), and Hg(II) present. The end point is violet-blue or light wine-red. Hg^{2+} is then determined as before by adding KI and titrating with a standard acid, the end point being

clear blue. CuR_2^{2-} remains unaffected by KI while HgR_2^{2-} is broken down to HgI_4^{2-} ; if the amount of Cu(II) is known, the free acid is calculated by difference or *vice versa*.

EXPERIMENTAL

The mercury solution was taken in a flask, treated with excess [about 3 to 4 times the amount of Hg(II) present] of the prepared reagent (K HR). The volume at this stage was kept about 50 ml. After adding 8 drops of 0.1% ethanolic solution of phenolphthalein, it was titrated with a standard alkali solution till a pink colour appeared. The amount of alkali consumed was equivalent to the sum of the free acid and Hg(II) present. To this solution excess of KI (ca. 2g.) was added, when the colour of the solution changed to deep pink due to liberation of alkali. This was titrated with the standard acid solution. The amounts of Hg(II) and free acid, taken and found by estimation, are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Hg soln. taken.	Hg present.	Alkali reqd.	Acid reqd.	Free acid found.	Hg found.
15 ml	153.90 mg.	*49.60 ml	34.85 ml	0.1686M	154.10 mg.
10	102.60	*33.10	23.20	0.1694	102.60
8	82.08	*26.50	18.60	0.1693	82.24
5	51.30	36.50	11.65	0.1694	51.51
3	30.78	21.80	7.00	0.1682	30.94
2	20.52	14.60	†20.55	0.1695	20.62
1	10.26	7.30	†10.30	0.1693	10.33

*These titrations were done with an alkali of strength 0.0821N, the rest with an alkali of strength 0.0373N.

†These titrations were made with a 0.010N-HCl, the rest with 0.04408N- H_2SO_4 .

TABLE II

Salt.	Foreign ions added.	Hg taken.	Acid reqd: (0.04408N- H_2SO_4).	Amount found.
KCl	0.05 g.	0.1026 g.	23.20 ml	0.10260 g.
"	0.10	0.1026	23.10	0.10210
"	0.20	0.1026	22.90	0.10130
"	0.50	0.1026	22.70	0.10030
"	1.00	0.1026	22.50	0.09950
K_2SO_4	1.00	0.1026	23.20	0.10260
NaAc	1.00	0.0821	18.60	0.08224
$\text{Cu(NO}_3)_2$	0.03	0.0513	11.60	0.05130
"	0.05	0.0513	11.55	0.05106
"	0.07	0.0513	11.70	0.05174
"	0.10	0.0513	11.70	0.05174
"	0.15	0.0513	11.50	0.05086

Interference by Foreign Ions.—Acetate, sulphate, copper (II), and chloride did not interfere in the determination of Hg(II) when present in small amounts. If the amount of

copper was high, the deep blue colour due to CuR_2^{2-} made the detection of the end point difficult. With low copper concentration [$<0.1\text{g Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ per $\sim 80\text{ml}$], the detection of the end point (appearing as violet-blue or light wine-red) was easier and provided more or less accurate results. Dilution (*ca.* 150 ml) or addition of a slight excess of phenolphthalein helped to obviate this difficulty. An approximate idea of the degree of interference is shown in Table II.

All solutions were prepared with CO_2 -free water and the reagents used were of A.R. quality or were properly purified.

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